

Link Prediction in Bibliographic Networks

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Abstract. Analysing bibliographic networks is important for understanding the process of scientific publications. A bibliographic network can be studied using the framework of Heterogeneous Information Networks (HINs). In this paper, we comparatively evaluate two different algorithms for link prediction in HINs on an instance of a bibliographic network. These two algorithms represent two distinct categories: algorithms that use path-related features of the graph and algorithms that use node embeddings. The results suggest that the path-based algorithms achieve significantly better performance on bibliographic networks.

1 Introduction

Analysing information about scientific papers, authors and venues provides useful insight into the scientific process. This information is often represented as a network, where authors are connected with their papers, and papers with the venues where they were published. This kind of network is referred to as a *bibliographic network*. Link prediction is the task of modelling the formation of edges in a network. In a bibliographic network, link prediction can be useful for various reasons, including recommendation of papers or venues, discovery of information that may be missing from the original dataset, and for gaining insights into the connectivity patterns of the networks, and consequently into the publication process.

From a data management perspective, a bibliographic network falls into the wider category of Heterogeneous Information Networks (HINs). A HIN is a graph, i.e., a set of nodes and edges, with the additional property that there are multiple *types* of nodes and edges. The existence of multiple types is important for modelling the graph. In particular, a sequence of node and edge types of a HIN is called a *metapath*. A metapath represents a composite relation between two nodes. For example, in a bibliographic network, the relation $Author \xrightarrow{writes} Paper \xrightarrow{isPublishedAt} Venue$ is a metapath that connects an author to a venue in which she has published a paper. The concept of metapath is important for link prediction algorithms in HINs. These algorithms can be categorised in two main categories: (a) those that are based on graph topology, i.e., that focus directly on the metapaths that exist between any two nodes [1–4], and

(b) those that use embeddings, which use low dimensional vector representations of the nodes of the graph [5–7].

In this paper, we compare the performance of two algorithms, representing the two mentioned categories, on the task of predicting links on a bibliographic network. The evaluation is performed on the DBLP dataset, which has two types of edges, using multiple metrics. The results suggest that, for this type of data, the graph topology based method achieves better results.

2 Related Work

Existing algorithms for link prediction in HINs can be distinguished in two main categories, depending on whether they are based on counting the metapaths between any two given nodes or on embeddings. The idea of counting the instances of a metapath to determine the relationship between two nodes first appears in [1], where a similarity measure between nodes based on the number of instances of a given metapath between them is proposed. Based on this, the counts of all metapaths are used in [2, 3] as features for a logistic regression model, trained for link prediction in an instance of the DBLP bibliographic network. The same metapath-count based model has also been used in [4] to predict the time that a link will occur, which is useful in datasets where time information is available.

Most of the recent work on link prediction in HINs belongs to the category of embedding based methods. In these, each node is represented by a low-dimensional vector of real numbers. Edge types may also have a vector or matrix representation, depending on the specific method. Link prediction is then performed through calculations of these representations. Various ways of obtaining and using embeddings have been proposed. Notably, in [5], node embeddings are obtained via metapath-constrained random walks. For each node, and for each given metapath, a large number of random walks are executed. The resulting node sequences are given as input to the skip-gram algorithm [5], which makes the inner product between the vectors of two nodes smaller, if these nodes are encountered closely in the random walks. In [6], embeddings are also obtained through random walks. However, in this case, a different embedding is first obtained for each metapath, and then all embeddings are combined in order to predict the existing links. In [7], each node is represented with a vector and each edge type is represented with a matrix. In this case, the node vectors are multiplied by the relation matrix and the euclidean distance is calculated from the resulting vectors, to predict the probability that an edge exists.

3 Description of Methods

3.1 Bibliographic Network

For our evaluation, we use a bibliographic network produced by the DBLP dataset. This dataset contains information on major computer science publications of the last five decades. Specifically it contains authors, papers, venues, and their relations. Next, we formulate the DBLP dataset as a HIN.

Fig. 1: The schema of the DBLP bibliographic network.

Formally, a HIN H is defined as $H = (V, E, L_V, L_E)$, where V is the set of nodes, E is the set of edges, L_V is the set of node types, and L_E is the set of edge types. For the DBLP network the node types are $L_V = \{Author, Paper, Venue\}$, while the edge types are $L_E = \{writes, isWrittenBy, publishes, isPublishedAt\}$. The way that the node types are connected, via the edge types, is represented by the network schema of H , which is shown in Figure 1. For example, nodes of type *Author* are connected with edges of type *writes* to nodes of type *Papers*. A metapath is a path on the network schema of H . For example, $Author \xrightarrow{writes} Paper \xrightarrow{isPublishedAt} Venue$ is a metapath that connects an author to a venue he has published in. Since the edge types can be inferred from the node types, we refer to the metapaths using only their node types, i.e., $Author \rightarrow Paper \rightarrow Venue$, or $A - P - V$ for short.

3.2 Metapath-Counts

Metapath-Counts algorithm [2] models the probability of a link existing between two nodes as a function of the number of metapaths that connect them. The model is developed for each edge type separately. For edge type $l_e \in L_E$, there exists a set $R_m(l_e)$, with size $|R_m(l_e)| = d(l_e)$, comprising all metapaths up to length m which connect the node types corresponding to l_e . For convenience, we enumerate the metapaths of $R_m(l_e)$ as r_{i,l_e} , $1 \leq i \leq d(l_e)$.

For a pair of nodes u, v and a metapath r , we define function $c(r, u, v)$ which returns the number of instances of metapath r that exists between u and v (e.g., the number of publications of an author to a venue). The vector of metapath counts between nodes u, v is defined as $\mathbf{x}_{l_e} : x_{i,l_e} = c(r_{i,l_e}, u, v)$. Then the probability that an edge of type l_e exists between u and v is modeled as:

$$p_{l_e}(u, v) = \sigma(\mathbf{x}_{l_e} \cdot \mathbf{w} + b) \quad (1)$$

where σ is the logistic sigmoid function, $\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}}$, and \cdot is the inner product operator. Vector \mathbf{w} contains the weights given by the model to the counts of the different metapaths and b is a constant bias on the probability.

To train the model for edge type l_e , we select all pairs u, v of H that are connected with an edge of type l_e in set $P(l_e)$. We also define a set of node pairs z, y , of the node types defined by l_e , that do not have an edge between

them, which we denote as $N(l_e)$. Since bibliographic networks tend to be sparse, which means that the size of $P(l_e)$ is $O(n)$, while $N(l_e)$ is $O(n^2)$, we do not include all pairs without an edge in $N(l_e)$. Instead we select a random sample. The technique of selecting a sample of the “negative” (non existing) edges is called negative sampling and is widely used in link prediction [7]. We select the negative sample in two steps. First, for each pair $u, v \in P(l_e)$, we randomly select α nodes y , of the same node type as v , from the m step neighborhood of u , asserting that edge does not exist ($y \notin P(l_e)$). Then, we randomly select α nodes y , of the same node type as v , from all nodes $V \setminus P(l_e)$, again asserting that the edge does not exist. Finally, the parameters are obtained by maximizing the log-likelihood on sets $P(l_e)$, $N(l_e)$:

$$L_{l_e}(\mathbf{w}, b) = \sum_{(u,v) \in P(l_e)} \log(p_{l_e}(u, v)) + \sum_{(u,v) \in N(l_e)} \log(1 - p_{l_e}(u, v)) \quad (2)$$

This function asserts that the probability that the model assigns to existing edges is as close to 1 as possible, while the probability that it assigns to non connected pairs is as close to 0 as possible. We note that in [2] a few other variations of the metapath-count features are also described, however we focus on the ones described in this section for conceptual and computational simplicity.

3.3 Metapath2Vec

Metapath2Vec algorithm [5] assigns a vector representation for each node of the HIN, based on its proximity to other nodes, and models the probability of a link as a function of these representations. The proximity is calculated via metapath constrained random walks on the HIN. Formally, each node v_i is associated with d dimensional representation \mathbf{x}_i . The probability that a link exists between v_i and v_j is modeled as:

$$p(v_i, v_j) = \frac{e^{\mathbf{x}_i \cdot \mathbf{x}_j}}{\sum_{v_k \in V} e^{\mathbf{x}_i \cdot \mathbf{x}_k}} \quad (3)$$

The algorithm receives a set of metapaths R as input. For each metapath $r \in R$ it performs I random walks of length k on the graph. At each step of the random walk, it chooses uniformly at random one of the available neighbors, having the type that is defined by metapath r . Subsequently, for each node v , the algorithm creates a multiset $C(v)$ containing all nodes that were encountered in a distance of w or less steps from v , for every random walk. Vectors x_i are randomly initialized and optimized via gradient descent so that they maximize the following log likelihood:

$$L = \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in C(v)} \log(p(v_i, v_j)) \quad (4)$$

Equation 4 require $O(n)$ evaluations of Equation 3 which itself has $O(n)$ complexity, for calculating the denominator. To avoid this complexity, negative sampling is used. Specifically α nodes v_k (Equation 3) are sampled uniformly at random from all nodes in V with the same type as v_i . We note that Metapath2Vec models all edge types simultaneously.

4 Evaluation

We evaluate the two algorithms on a large sample of the DBLP dataset. We select a sample, instead of using the entire DBLP dataset, to limit the computational requirements of the experiments. This sample consists of authors, papers and venues from the academic field of data management. We obtain it by finding all venues that contain the word “data” in their title, and select the venues, the papers published in these venues and their authors. In total, the sample consists of 507 venues, 374,034 authors, and 357,091 papers, that span the time period from 1969 to 2017, with the majority occurring in the last 10 years of the dataset. The evaluation is performed separately for each of the two distinct edge types: “Writes” and “Publishes”. In each case we use 70% of the edges for training, 10% for validation/tuning and 20% for testing.

For each algorithm, we evaluate the performance in link prediction using three metrics: MeanRank, HITS@10 and MeanReciprocalRank(MRR). These measures are calculated by comparing the scores of positive and negative edges (i.e., edges that exist in the graph and edges that do not exist in the graph). We select the negative samples using the technique described in 3.2, with $\alpha = 50$. MeanRank corresponds to the mean rank of the score of the positive edges, if the algorithm is applied to all edges and the results are sorted in descending order. For MeanRank lower values are better and the optimal value is 1. To calculate HITS@10 and MRR, we partition all edges (u, v) (positive and negative) according to their starting node u . For each partition, we apply the algorithms and sort the scores in descending order. Hits@10 is the number of positive edges in the 10 higher scores, for each partition. MRR is the inverse of the rank of the first positive edge, for each partition. For HITS@10, MRR higher score are better, and the optimal values are 10,1 respectively.

The results are presented in Table 1. We see that MetapathCounts achieves a better score for both edge types and according to all metrics. The difference is larger for MeanRank metric, while it is not so large for HITS@10 and MRR metrics. This means that, while Metapath2Vec correctly identifies links that have high probability to exist, it does not manage to correctly differentiate between links that have medium and small probability to exist. On the other hand MetapathCounts achieves better performance for all edges, both those that are very likely to exist and those that exist with smaller probability than others. A possible explanation for the difference in performance of these two algorithms is that bibliographic networks, such as the DBLP network, tend to be too sparse for the embedding algorithm to be trained adequately.

Another interesting aspect of MetapathCounts algorithm is that it provides a weight for the importance of each metapath, optimized for the task of link prediction. The weights for our experimental setting are presented in Table 2. Metapath A-P-A-P, exists between author A_1 and paper P_1 , when P_1 has another author A_2 that has been a coauthor with A_1 on another paper P_2 . On the other side, metapath P-A-P-V exists when A_1 and A_2 have published to a common venue. The coefficients of Table 2 suggest that the relationship between coauthors is more important than the relationship between authors that have published to

Edge Type	Writes			Publishes		
	MeanRank	HITS@10	MRR	MeanRank	HITS@10	MRR
MetapathCounts	31815	3.88	0.95	30417	5.40	0.72
Metapath2Vec	53450	3.85	0.92	41570	4.70	0.71

Table 1: Link Prediction Scores

Metapath	A-P-A-P	A-P-V-P	P-A-P-V
Coefficient	2.019	0.067	0.300

Table 2: Metapath Coefficients

the same venue, and they also offer a quantification of this difference. This can be useful for various analytic tasks, such as estimating the importance of nodes. Also MetapathCounts is a simpler model, with significantly less parameters, than Metapath2Vec or other embedding models.

These results suggest that MetapathCounts is more effective than Metapath2Vec for modelling a bibliographic network. This is an interesting result and motivates the further improvement of the framework defined by MetapathCounts algorithm. A possible direction of improvement would be to include additional features, such as year of publication, into the formulation of the model.

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References

1. *PathSim: Meta Path-Based Top-K Similarity Search in Heterogeneous Information Networks*. Y. Sun, J. Han, X. Yan, P. S. Yu, T. Wu. VLDB, 2011.
2. *Co-author Relationship Prediction in Heterogeneous Bibliographic Networks*. Y. Sun, R. Barber, M. Gupta, C. C. Aggarwal, J. Han. ASONAM, 2011.
3. *Citation prediction in heterogeneous bibliographic networks*. X. Yu, Q. Gu, M. Zhou, J. Han. SDM, 2012.
4. *When will it happen?: Relationship prediction in heterogeneous information networks*. Y. Sun, J. Han, C. C. Aggarwal, and N. V. Chawla. WSDM, 2012.
5. *metapath2vec: Scalable Representation Learning for Heterogeneous Networks*. Y. Dong, N. Chawla, A. Swami. KDD, 2017.
6. *Heterogeneous Information Network Embedding for Recommendation*. C. Shi, B. Hu, W. X. Zhao, P. s. Yu. TKDE, 2019.
7. *PME: Projected Metric Embedding on Heterogeneous Networks for Link Prediction*. H. Chen, H. Yin, W. Wang, H. Wang, Q. Nguyen, X. Li. KDD, 2018.